

The Constitution- Freedoms and Rights

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Abstract

People often view the framing of India's Constitution as a pivotal point in history since it marked the end of a long-running fight for political and economic self-determination and the passage from a colonial government maintained by coercion to a democratic republic. Basically, Part-3rd of the Constitution the Fundamental Rights is the basic rights of humans and guaranteed by the Constitution of India. Thereafter, the fundamental rights² put in with the "Right to Equality", "Right to freedom", "Right against exploitation", "Right to freedom of Religion", "Cultural and Educational Rights" and "Right to constitutional Remedies". Freedom grants people the fundamental rights to "freedom of speech", "association, personal liberty", and "the right to live a dignified life", among other things. The extent of these regulations and any applicable exceptions must be understood. The purpose of this article is to offer understanding into the Indian Constitution, which is founded on the values of "liberty", "equality", "fraternity", and "justice". The study also discusses freedom and rights from a fundamental point of view.

Key words: Indian Constitution, Constitutional Remedies, Fundamental rights, Democratic, Value of Justice.

Introduction

The fundamental framework of the political system under which a nation's citizens are to be governed is laid out in its constitution. It creates the primary state legislative, executive, and judicial branches and outlines their respective roles, responsibilities, and connections with the public. However, "every constitution is built on the political and economic ethos, faith, and aspirations of the people", and it represents the founders' goals and principles. It is important to keep in mind that a constituent assembly is considered and approved by the people who draft the constitution of a sovereign democratic nation. To ensure that all Indian people can live peaceful and harmonious lives, civil rights are guaranteed in Part III (Article 12-35) of the Indian Constitution. These rights are referred to as "fundamental" because they are essential for the development of the whole person, which includes the development of the body, mind, morality, and soul. They are also guaranteed by the constitution, which is the fundamental law of the land. Among these are the "constitutional remedies rights to writs such as habeas corpus for the protection of civil rights. These include individual rights like "equality before the law," "freedom of speech and expression," "the right to peaceful assembly and association," and "the freedom to practice one's religion," which are shared by most liberal democracies. The consequences for violating these rights are outlined in the Indian Penal Code and are left up to the judge's interpretation. Every Indian citizen has the right to the fundamental liberties required for their own harmonious and well-being. All citizens are entitled to these rights, regardless of their gender, race, caste, religion, place of birth, or any other attribute. They are 3 enforceable by the courts and are subject to limits. Among the several texts that form the basis for the rights are the French Declaration of Human Rights, the English Bill of Rights, and the United States Bill of Rights.

Basic Rights⁴:

“Rights to equality” (Article 14–18), “Freedom of speech” (Article 19–22), “Right against exploitation” (Article 23–24), “Religion-related freedom” (Article 25–28), “Cultural Rights and Educational Rights” (Article 29–30), “Constitutional remedies are guaranteed” (Article 32).

Preamble With Freedom And Rights View

The Constitution's Preamble is of utmost significant, and it should be read and interpreted in the context of the lofty and honorable goal it sets forth. "We the people of India, having solemnly resolved to constitute India into a sovereign, socialist, secular, democratic republic and to secure to all citizens: Justice, social, economic and political; View of Liberty of thoughts, expression, belief (Trust), faith, and worship; Equality of status and of opportunity; and to promote among them all, Fraternity assuring the dignity of the individual and the unity and integrity of the nation" is how the Preamble of the Constitution is phrased. The Preamble, which expresses the aspirations of the people who founded the Constitution, succinctly lays out the Quintessence of human rights. The Indian "Constitution is distinctive in that a significant portion of human rights are designated as Fundamental Rights, and the power to enforce Fundamental Rights itself has been elevated to the status of a Fundamental Right". The Indian Constitution's "list of fundamental rights is the Magna Carta of human rights and individual liberty. Individuals have rights based on their right to equality, right to freedom, right against exploitation", right to freedom of religion, and right to cultural and educational rights under the Fundamental Rights under Articles "14 to 31" of the Constitution.

These Rights can be categorized into Several Groups:

Equal Opportunity (Art. 14-18)

The fundamental human right recognized by the Indian Constitution is the **right to equality**. While Article 14⁵ asserts that "the state shall not deny to any person within the territory of India, equality before the law and equal protection of the laws," Article 15⁶ is much more detailed and states that "the state shall not discriminate against any citizen on the basis of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth, or any of them be subject to any disability, liability, restriction, or condition with regard to (a) access to shops, public restaurants, hotels, and plazas". Whereas Article-16th of the Constitution says that "all citizens should have an equal opportunity in matters relating to employment or appointment to any office under the state." Untouchability and titles are to be abolished according to Articles 17 and 18, respectively.

Right to Freedom (Art. 19-22)

The foundation of "Indian human rights are found in articles 19 through 22 that guarantee freedom." Importantly, Article 19⁷ states that "all citizens shall have the right to freedom of speech and expression; the right to assemble in peace and without weapons; the right to form associations or unions; the right to move freely throughout the territory of India; the right to abode and settle in any part of the territory of India; and basic valuable right to practice any profession or to engage in any occupation, trade, or business". As opposed to "Article-20 of the Constitution, which provides that no person shall be convicted of any crime unless for violation of a law in force at the time the act accused as an offence, nor shall he be punished with a fine exceeding that which may have been imposed under the law in force at the time of the commission of the offence." However, "Article 20's statement that no person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except pursuant to the method established by law is the most significant statement" regarding human freedom.

Right Against Exploitation (Art. 23-24)

In "Articles-23 & 24, the Constitution lists a number of rights that are protected from exploitation, human trafficking, and other forms of similar exploitation. Human "trafficking, beggaring, and other forms of forced labour are all prohibited by Article 23." Instead of the more general term "slavery," our Constitution uses the phrase "traffic in human beings," which forbids the "trade in women, children, and handicapped people for immoral or other purposes in addition to servitude. Article 24 of the Constitution forbids the employment of children under the age of 14 in any mine, factory, or other

dangerous job. As a result, forced labour is forbidden, and minors are now safeguarded in accordance with fundamental rights."

Right To Freedom Of Religion (Art. 25-28)

Certain religious freedoms for residents are prescribed in "Part-III of the Constitution under Articles 25 to 28". They "consist of the right to administer religious affairs, the right to practice and spread one's religion freely, the right to pay taxes to support a particular religion, and the right to attend religious instruction or worship in specified educational institutions. These are essential religious minorities' rights in India, to put it briefly".

Cultural and Educational Rights (Art. 29-30)

Certain cultural and educational rights are provided to the minority groups under Articles 29 and 30 of the Constitution⁸. Article 30 states that "all minorities, whether based on religion or language, shall have the right to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice." Article 29⁹ guarantees the right of any section of citizens residing in any part of the country

Right to Constitutional Remedies

These fundamental rights are being challenged by the provisions of laws like the "Maintenance of Internal Security Act" (MISA), "Armed Forces (Special Powers) Act" (AFSPA), and "National Security Act" (NSA), which sanction overreaching powers without regard for civil rights in the name of combating domestic and international terrorism and political violence. Public order, morality, and state security all have significant implications. The meaning of terms like "reasonable restrictions" and "the interest of public order" is not explicitly stated in the Constitution¹⁰, and this ambiguity causes needless litigation. Although people are allowed to assemble peacefully and without weapons, the police may occasionally break up these gatherings using non-lethal means. In terms of upholding these rights, Chapter III of the Indian Constitution, which deals with fundamental rights, has some judicial protection. Every person has the right, under Article 32, to petition the Supreme Court (Apex Court) in the appropriate proceedings for the enforcement of the rights granted by Part III. The Supreme Court is given the authority to issue writs under Clause 2 of this Article, including writs of habeas corpus, mandamus, prohibition, quo warranto, and certiorari. Except in situations where a proclamation of emergency is in effect, this privilege cannot be suspended. The interests of India's sovereignty, unity, and integrity are not affected by fundamental human rights like freedom of speech and expression, peaceful assembly without force, or the formation of associations or unions, according to Article 19 of Part III of the Constitution. The Constitution encourages the Indian people to nurture and model the virtues of integrity and sovereignty, but forbids their application in relation to Indian territory. India (Bharat) is referred to as a Union of States in Article 1 of Part 1 of the Indian Constitution. In a word, the Constitution declares that India "is its people, not its land."

By outlining fundamental rules of government, this charter of positive rights aims to promote social, political, and economic justice for all. These principles are meant to be kept in mind by both the legislative and executive branches of government when making and executing laws. Despite these guidelines are vital to the country's governance even though they cannot be enforced by a court, and it is the State's responsibility to use these principles when drafting laws for the general public. Protection of their children, women, and men.

They are as follows:

- Offering sufficient means of subsistence "(Article-39 (a)". Total pay for equal work for men and women "(Article 39(d))"
- Adequate safeguards for the well-being and power of employees, both men and women- "(Article 39(e))"
- Equal Justice and No-Cost Legal Assistance- "(Article 39 A)"
- A living wage, working conditions that permit the full use of free time and social and cultural

- possibilities “(Article 43)”.
- Children's education is free and required-“(Article 45)”.
 - Improving public health, raising living standards, and enhancing nutrition-“(Article 47)”
 - Forbids the slaughter of cows, calves, and other milk and draught cattle-“(Article 48)”.

The Directive Principles of State Policy, or Part IV of the Constitution, lists a plethora of civil and economic rights for Indian citizens. They serve as India's foundation for human rights.

Conclusion

Rights literally refer to those liberties that are necessary for both individual and societal well-being. The Fundamental Law of the Land and the ability to enforce them in a court of law make the rights guaranteed by the Indian Constitution fundamental. But this does not imply that they are infallible or unaffected by constitutional reform. A thorough examination¹¹ of the “Fundamental Rights” (freedoms and Rights) demonstrates how almost the whole scope of the “Universal Declaration of Human Rights” is covered by the Constitution and its ramifications. Additionally, through these two portions (Parts III and IV), the Indian Constitution has made a creative endeavor to strike a equilibrium between rights that are enforced and rights that are not, allowing them to support one another in terms of the basic governance of the nation. Finally, it should be noted that these two rights are intertwined and necessary for others to be fed.

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